

FUTURE MATHEMATICS SCIENCE TEACHERS MATHEMATICS FROM SCIENCE APPROPRIATION DIFFICULT HAS BEEN VISUAL TEACHING OF ISSUES METHODOLOGY (UNITS AND POLYNOMIALS EXAMPLE)

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Annotation: This in the article student old people and future mathematics science teachers united and polynomials on the subject interests and mathematics science circle interests increase and to teach facilitate ways done increase for manual task performs A lot and united topic to teach for didactic games are also an example as given.

Key word: Monomials and polynomials, examples and didactic games and to teach methodology.

Polynomials and they are on deeds to perform the most first of all polynomials what the fact that about common information have to be need _

Polynomials about common concepts from being given first while numerous and with letters expressions about common data and concepts input it is necessary Numerical and with letters expressions about concepts as letters and of thighs mixture ie common from the hossa come out without done increase can _

Numerical and with letters expressions about common concepts from given after while united from him after while polynomials about general to concepts and polynomials on to actions our passage to the goal according to will be

Monomials as given rational in expression Participant letter on two action, multiplication and to the degree raise as a result harvest was to expression it is said.

It was given together increase degree with replacing, initially unchanging stretch your thigh in it attended t e bricked the letters in order if written, yield was to expression of one standard it looks nice. Letters in front of numerous to the sender of one the coefficient is e nti d e.

Polynomials are one of the main branches of algebra, which includes many concepts. To be able to perform operations on polynomials, to master the science of algebra well, to solve related concepts and various problems: for example, it is possible to easily solve problems such as compacting algebraic fractions, making

expressions into a standard form, revealing some ambiguities in the theory of limits gives

In this manual, $P_n(x)$ operations performed on n-natural number polynomials, definitions and theorems specific to this direction, and examples of solving polynomial examples are described.

Monomials refers to the expression formed as a result of two operations, multiplication and raising to the level, on the factor letter in the given rational expression.

For example: $2a$; $3abc$; $\frac{13abc}{12}$; $\frac{3}{5}ab$; a^2b ; xy^4 etc

If we replace the multiplication with degree in the given unit, and first write the constant number, then the letters involved in it in the appropriate order, the resulting expression is called **the standard** form of the unit. The numerical multiplier in front of the letters is called the coefficient of unity.

For example: $3abc \cdot 5ac \cdot \frac{2}{13}bc$ **the standard** form of a word is $i \frac{30}{13}a^2b^2c^3$ b will die.

The sum of two or more terms is called polynomial. So, the polynomial consists of the algebraic sum of these units.

Equations that differ only by their coefficients are called similar equations.

For example: $5ab$ and $-3ab$ or $15x^2y^3$ and $7x^2y^3$ are similar because the coefficients are different and the literal expressions are the same. When solving many problems, the question arises as to when two polynomials are equal to each other. The following theorem answers this question.

Theorem 1: If two polynomials x are the coefficients in front of corresponding degrees of

if equal, such polynomials are mutually equal.

For example: $P_2(x) = 3x^2 - 7x + 4$ and $Q_2(x) = Ax^2 + Bx + C$ $A=3$ to be in views ; $P_2(x) = Q_2(x)$ $V=-7$; It should be $S=4$. Here is an example of the application of this theorem:

$P_3(x) = x^3 + 3x + 4$ it is necessary to express a polynomial of the third degree as a product of one polynomial of the first and one of the second degree.

So, we express the polynomial of the first and second degree in the following form: $x + A$ and $Bx^2 + Cx + D$ according to the condition of the problem $x^3 + 3x + 4 = (x + A)(Bx^2 + Cx + D)$, we open the bracket on the right side of the equality and equate the coefficients in front of the same levels of x.

$$x^3 + 3x + 4 = Bx^3 + Cx^2 + Dx + ABx^2 + ACx + AD \text{ or}$$

$$x^3 + 3x + 4 = Bx^3 + (C + AB)x^2 + (D + AC)x + AD \text{ or}$$

$$x^3 + 0 \cdot x^2 + 3 \cdot x + 4 = Bx^3 + (C + AB)x^2 + (D + AC)x + AD \text{ if we equate:}$$

$B = 1, A = 1, C = -1, D = 4$ we find that

So, $x^3 + 3x + 4 = (x + 1)(x^2 - x + 4)$ it will be.

We can use a didactic game to facilitate the teaching of general information about the differences of monomials and polynomials and to provide information about general concepts.

As a didactic game, it is appropriate to use a didactic game called basket.

As for the content aspect of this game, the students are placed in front of several cards with problems and two small baskets are placed for the students to separate their understanding of the information about the polynomials and polynomials. It is recommended to put hadds in one basket and many khads in another basket. In this way, the reader serves to develop young people's understanding of the distinction between singulars and plurals and their thoughts about general concepts.

Students and young people helps to increase their interest in the subject as well as increase their interest in mathematics.

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